

USE OF MODERN INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING ENGLISH

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Annotation: This article highlights the importance attached to foreign languages in the Republic of Uzbekistan and the innovative technologies needed to study them.

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After the independence of our country, the interest in teaching foreign languages has increased and many opportunities have been created for young people. As the first President Islam Karimov said, “At present, great importance is attached to teaching foreign languages in our country. This, of course, is not in vain. Today, the world community does not need to underestimate the importance of perfect knowledge of foreign languages for our countries, which are striving to take a worthy place, for our people, who are building their great future in cooperation with our foreign partners. As a logical continuation of these ideas, the Presidential Decree of December 10, 2012 "On measures to further improve the system of teaching foreign languages" expanded the opportunities for learning foreign languages.

New methods and requirements for teaching a foreign language in our country have been developed in accordance with the Recommendations of the European Framework for Assessment of Knowledge and Skills of Foreign Language Teachers (CEFR). According to him, textbooks have been created for students of secondary schools and vocational colleges. In accordance with these requirements, classrooms are equipped with stands and new information and communication techniques. The demand for learning a foreign language is also growing day by day. Foreign

language science is divided into four aspects (reading, reading, listening comprehension and speaking), each of which is given a separate understanding and skills. Educational technology is the effective use of modern information technology in the educational process. as well as improving the quality and effectiveness of education through the introduction of modern innovative technologies in the educational process. In particular, there are several advantages to using such information and communication technologies in learning a foreign language.

The role of modern technology in language learning and teaching is invaluable. The use of technological tools is useful in every aspect of learning a foreign language (reading, reading, listening comprehension and speaking). For example, to listen and understand, of course, it is impossible to do this process without a computer, player, CDs. Listening comprehension is one of the most important parts of language learning. At the same time, the student is required to pay attention to the pronunciation of the speaker, adherence to grammatical rules, vocabulary and its meanings. An important factor in the use of modern technologies in education is the ability of students to know and use information and communication technologies. Teaching and learning a foreign language using modern technology is one of the most effective methods. The basis of the use of game technology is the activity that activates and accelerates the reader. Psychologists point out that the psychological mechanisms of playful activity are based on the fundamental needs of the individual to express himself, to find a stable place in life, to self-manage, to realize his potential. At the heart of any game should be generally accepted educational principles, tactics. Learning games should be based on learning subjects. During the games, the student is more interested in this activity than in a normal lesson and works more comfortably. It should be noted that the game is, first of all, a way of teaching. Students participate in play lessons with interest, strive to win, and the teacher also educates the student through them. We know that in the current educational process, the learner must be a subject. At

the same time, focusing on more interactive methods increases the effectiveness of education. One of the most important requirements for English lessons is to teach students to think independently.

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